

Linked Open Datasets on Garments from the Latgale Region

Data description and data access points

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The data published were collected within Ieva Pigozne’s postdoctoral research “Development of Folk Dress in Latgale in the 19th Century” (1.1.1.2/VIAA/1/16/092) in 2018-2020.

The main goal of [TextileBase](#) is to help dress history scholars and practitioners by creating a gateway to linked data that have been collected and stored by researchers and memory institutions. In that way it is a platform to collect, connect, and share meta- and research data on material, visual, and textual sources of historical clothing. We explain [TextileBase](#) as a linked, open, graph database in a different report. In this review we show how we placed a valuable, stand-alone dataset into this interoperable database.

Figure 1: You can try out TextileBase on <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/index.php>. Example items: [Q142](#), [Q179](#), [Q180](#), [Q181](#).

The first published dataset contains data on Latvian traditional shirts and skirts from the Latgale region in Eastern Latvia.

The **shirts** in the dataset are handmade and were worn in the 19th century. They represent both festive and daily wear of the local female and male peasants. The shirts are stored at the *National History Museum of Latvia* and the *Ethnographic Open-Air Museum of Latvia*. The data contain information on the locality of their origin, their approximate date of creation with various precisions, the materials they are made of, and the way of their fabrication, as well as their purpose of wearing (festive or daily wear) and wearer’s ethnicity and gender. They also include the name of the museum each shirt is stored at, supplemented with its unique inventory number. Data on some sample shirts also include a photo of the shirt.

ID	label	description	datatype
shirt			
txb:Q147	female festive shirt (CVVM 12664)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1st half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q148	female festive shirt (CVVM 12665)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1st half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q149	male festive shirt (CVVM 12666)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1844 or later)	wikibase-item
txb:Q150	female festive shirt (CVVM 12667)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q151	female festive shirt (CVVM 12711)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q152	male festive shirt (CVVM 12721)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q153	female festive shirt (CVVM 12753)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q154	female festive shirt (CVVM 12758)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q155	female festive shirt (CVVM 12759)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1887 or later)	wikibase-item
txb:Q156	female festive shirt (CVVM 12761)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q157	female festive shirt (CVVM 12764)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1830 or later)	wikibase-item
txb:Q158	female festive shirt (CVVM 12765)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q159	female festive shirt (CVVM 12769)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q160	female festive shirt (CVVM 12770)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q161	female festive shirt (CVVM 12771)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q162	female festive shirt (CVVM 12774)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1850 or later)	wikibase-item
txb:Q163	female festive shirt (CVVM 12775)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q164	female festive shirt (CVVM 12777)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (End of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q165	male festive shirt (CVVM 12787)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1877 or later)	wikibase-item

(continued)

ID	label	description	datatype
txb:Q166	female festive shirt (CVVM 12811)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1898 or later)	wikibase-item
txb:Q167	female daily wear shirt (CVVM 12812)	daily wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q168	female festive shirt (CVVM 12814)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q169	male daily wear shirt (CVVM 12816)	daily wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q170	male daily wear shirt (CVVM 12817)	daily wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q171	female festive shirt (CVVM 12818)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q172	female daily wear shirt (CVVM 12821)	daily wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q173	male festive shirt (CVVM 12822)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q174	female festive shirt (CVVM 27275)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q175	male festive shirt (CVVM 27600)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q176	male festive shirt (CVVM 160961)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q177	female festive shirt (CVVM 172286)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q178	female festive shirt (CVVM 177640)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (1st half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q179	female festive shirt (BDM 4619)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q180	female festive shirt (BDM 4698)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q181	female festive shirt (BDM 4699)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q182	male shirt (BDM 4754)	male shirt from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item

The **skirts** in the dataset are handmade and were worn in the 19th century. They represent festive wear of the local female peasants. The skirts are stored at the *National History Museum of Latvia* and the *Preiļi Museum of History and Applied Arts*. The data contain information on the locality of their origin, their approximate date of creation with various precision, the materials they are made of, and the way of their fabrication, as well as their purpose of wearing (festive wear) and the wearer’s ethnicity and gender, which in this case is always female, as these type of skirts in the region were only worn by women. They also include the name of the museum each skirt is stored at, supplemented with its unique

inventory number. Data on some sample skirts also include a photo of the skirt.

ID	label	description	datatype
skirt			
txb:Q140	female festive skirt (CVVM 10765)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item
txb:Q142	female festive skirt (PVLMM 11516)	festive wear from Latgale region in Latvia (2nd half of the 19th century)	wikibase-item

The Short-term Scientific Mission “Collecting, Evaluating, and Connecting Data for Dress History” was carried out by Ieva Pigozne within the COST action “Europe through Textiles: Network for an integrated and interdisciplinary Humanities” (Euroweb) CA19131. During this short-term mission, we brought this format to an interoperable, linked, open data format to foster knowledge exchange and reuse.

Our task was to add a better structure to this database and to describe the data in a way that requires no outside knowledge of the schema or definitions used in the database. This kind of normalisation of the annotation allows other researchers to reuse and innovate with the dataset, and also enables the author to import data from different sources.

Our normalisation uses the RDF standard and two RDF-annotated conceptual and data models: CIDOC-CM (Bekiari et al. 2024), that is used to make museum collection data interoperable, and the Wikidata Data Model, which allows the use of the popular open knowledge graph editor Wikibase/Wikidata. CIDOC-CM has been represented in Wikibase successfully in many European and North American collections. (Pfeiffer and Gayo 2021; Rossenova, Duchesne, and Blümel 2022)

ID	label	description	datatype
properties			
txb:P3	instance of	type to which this subject corresponds/belongs. Different from P279 (subclass of); for example extdollar K2 is an instance of mountain; volcanoes form a subclass of mountains, and the volcano is a type (instance) of volcanic landform	wikibase-item
txb:P38	inventory number	identifier for a physical object or a set of physical objects in a collection	string
txb:P65	has current owner	the that agent has legal ownership over the object	wikibase-item
txb:P66	was made for	the garment was made for a specific activity; connects the human-made thing to an activity. (inverse property extdollar 'intended use')	wikibase-item
txb:P68	worn by	the garment was worn by specific type of people	wikibase-item
txb:P48	country of origin	country of origin of this item (creative work, food, phrase, product, etc.)	wikibase-item

(continued)

ID	label	description	datatype
txb:P60	creation time span	approximate time of creation or start of existance, refers to a period; when you know the exact creation or inception date, use the inception property	wikibase-item
txb:P33	inception	time when an entity begins to exist; do not use for the official opening date of an institution	point-in-time
txb:P34	made from material	material the subject or the object is made of or derived from (do not confuse with P10672 which is used for processes)	wikibase-item
txb:P35	fabrication method	method, process or technique used to grow, cook, weave, build, assemble, manufacture the item	wikibase-item
txb:P36	color	color of subject	wikibase-item

Our central transformation needed to transform the tabular dataset into a neural network-like graph. We connected various elements of a spreadsheet table so that they became elementary scientific statements. Scientific statements always take a subject-predicate-object form, with a scientifically verifiable true or false value. A particular shirt has a **white** colour. A particular skirt was made from the materials material, **wool** and **linen**.

Technically, we needed to convert Ieva Pigozne’s original datasets into Cobb’s third normal form, which data scientists often call tidy, and organise the data in a way that every observational unit (shirt) is in a row of the dataset, and each property is brought into relationship with this shirt in subsequent columns.

Bringing the dataset to a third normal form allows the translation to machine-readable and easily verifiable elementary scientific statements, but it does not necessarily make them readable for a fellow human researcher. Semantic structuring will initially require an information or data scientist, though our approach is straightforward and easy to copy in similar scenarios.

To open up and reuse the database and connect information in different organisations, we also have to ensure that all the new knowledge is understood similarly, for example, the concept of “blue”. As a colour, a dye, or a fabric, it has to be understood across natural languages (“blauw” in the Netherlands and “kék” in Hungary) or measured as the light (reflection) in the 477.5 ± 122.5 nanometre spectrum or described with the 0000FF sRGB colour hex triplet.

The following standardised vocabularies were used to describe the data:

Table 4: Vocabulary description

Name	Description
Wikidata	A multilingual linked open knowledge base hosted by the Wikimedia Foundation.
AAT	The Art & Architecture Thesaurus® is intended to provide terminology and other information about the fields of Art and Architecture.
Geonames	A linked open database of geographical names in the world.

The last step was to ensure that definitions of qualitative data, like the **blue** colour or the **2nd half of the 19th century** as approximate dating, are linked so that computers could read them into their databases and researchers could efficiently work with them across the countries. (See: [txb:Q69](#); [txb:Q112](#))

In the 19th century the territory of Latvia was part of the Russian Empire and closely connected to Germany. Therefore, terms like “shirt” and “blue” should be at least available in Latvian, German, Russian, and the new lingua franca, English.

We added links to the Art & Architecture Thesaurus® definitions to the qualitative data, but we also realised the shortcomings of this approach, which we will explain in a forthcoming publication.

The database can be accessed via https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/index.php?title=Main_Page; and under the DOI on the Zenodo record it can be accessed in Excel and CSV formats, too.

References

- Bekiari, Chryssoula, George Bruseke, Erin Canning, Martin Doerr, Philippe Michon, Christian-Emil Ore, Stephen Stead, and Velios Athanasios, eds. 2024. ‘Definition of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model’. CIDOC CRM Special Interest Group. https://www.cidoc-crm.org/sites/default/files/cidoc_crm_version_7.2.4.pdf.
- Pfeiffer, Michelle, and Jose Emilio Labra Gayo. 2021. ‘Representing CIDOC-CRM in Wikibase for the Luxembourg Shared Authority File’. <https://swib.org/swib21/slides/05-03-gayo.pdf>.
- Rossenova, Lozana, Paul Duchesne, and Ina Blümel. 2022. ‘Wikidata and Wikibase as Complementary Research Data Management Services for Cultural Heritage Data’. In *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*. https://serwiss.bib.hs-hannover.de/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/2573/file/rossenova_etal2022-wikidata_research_data_mgmt.pdf.